

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF ASSESSMENT BY MEDICAL WORKERS OF THEIR OWN HEALTH

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Abstract

The article analyzes the problem of health and healthy lifestyle of doctors and mid-level medical workers. The work examines the determinants of health, lifestyle and healthy lifestyle. As a result of the research, the results of the questionnaire were analyzed, conclusions were drawn regarding the attitude of doctors and medical personnel to their individual health, and the main postulates of the formation of a healthy lifestyle were highlighted.

Keywords: health workers, health, lifestyle, healthy lifestyle, risk factors, health levels, quality of life.

Introduction.

Strengthening and preserving the health of the Ukrainian population depends on the attitude of each person to his health. In connection with the Russian aggression, the aggravation of socio-economic problems, and the increase in stressful situations, the health of the Ukrainian population has significantly deteriorated. When transitioning to market relations, there is a change in economic relations, which similarly requires changes in the organization of the health care system, thereby starting its reformation, which primarily involves reforming primary health care [1].

In order to maintain your health for a long time, you need to start doing physical exercises, follow the rules of personal hygiene and lead an active lifestyle. The concept of "health" is closely connected with the concept of "healthy lifestyle". Lifestyle is the everyday behavior of a person, which includes all life processes: the regime of work and rest, material and spiritual needs, participation in public life. Approximately 90% of patients receive medical care based on the paradigm of health preservation and analysis of risk factors, receive a significant amount of medical and preventive care, which includes analysis of risk factors for the occurrence of diseases, etc. V. Horashchuk defines a healthy lifestyle as an activity aimed at the formation, preservation, strengthening and restoration of people's health, as conditions and prerequisites for implementation,

A healthy lifestyle includes a rational diet, moderate exercise, regular medical examinations, absence of bad habits: alcohol abuse, overeating, cigarette smoking, etc.

The formation of a healthy lifestyle directly depends on the model of formation of human behavior:

1. Conducting discussions about the benefits of health and the benefits of a healthy lifestyle.
2. Modification of human behavior.
3. Implementation of a healthy lifestyle in everyday life.

It should be noted that a person's behavior depends on his individual characteristics: his own values, personal self-esteem, and the surrounding environment. All these characteristics can change over time. Of

particular importance is the formation of a healthy lifestyle by correcting one's own lifestyle. A special place among the main methodological approaches in research is given, as in the theory, to the axiological approach: According to the theory of S.G. Dobrotvirskaya: "A healthy lifestyle is not only a way of organizing all aspects of life aimed at strengthening health and fulfilling generally accepted norms and rules of a healthy lifestyle." A healthy lifestyle is a lifestyle that corresponds to the genetically determined typological characteristics of a person, corresponding to specific living conditions. It is aimed at forming preservation and strengthening of health and the full fulfillment by a person of its sociobiological functions [5]. This category is aimed at forming a person's priority values regarding health, awareness of personal behavior and consideration of health components (mental, physiological, social).

Basic material

Undoubtedly, the way of life affects the future health of a person. The state of health in the future depends on the lifestyle chosen by a person. The formation of positive motivation for a healthy lifestyle should be an integral component of the activity and professional competence of a teacher (teacher of secondary education) [2]. Full health is impossible without the integration of such concepts as the totality of mental, intellectual, social, professional, moral and spiritual health. Lifestyle is a category that is determined by the following categories: level, quality and style of life. The standard of living is a person's satisfaction of economic, material and spiritual needs.

Quality of life is an assessment of a person's health not only at the individual level, but also at the population level. Considering this, the health assessment should be comprehensive and fully assess the physical, psychological, social and economic condition of the sick person. Since health is an important parameter of the quality of life, many attempts to define this concept were made in the field of medical sciences [5].

A review of the main approaches to assessing the quality of life gives grounds for concluding that it is a

multidimensional concept with a multicomponent structure. Traditionally, two conceptual approaches to assessing the quality of life are distinguished: objective and subjective [4]. Assessment of the quality of life is analyzed not only on the basis of subjective assessment (satisfaction with life), but also on generally accepted properties.

Our research used: statistical method, system analysis method (analysis, synthesis, integration of research results) and questionnaire. In addition, we created a special questionnaire with a set of questions about the awareness of medical workers about their personal health. The study included the following procedure:

1. Development of a special questionnaire with a list of certain questions that are necessary to characterize the individual health of respondents for health care managers.

2. Analysis, synthesis and integration of the obtained results.

3. Conclusions and practical recommendations.

Goal: analyze the results of the questionnaire and draw conclusions about the attitude of doctors and medical staff to their individual health.

68 medical workers (30 doctors and 38 mid-level medical workers. Among them - 40 women (59%) and 28 men (41%) participated in the study.

Questionnaire questions were evaluated in points (gradation of 5 points). The following results were obtained for the questions of the questionnaire regarding the evaluation of the general state of personal health by doctors: 2.7% of respondents rated their state of health at 1 point, 5.4% - 2 points, 46% - 3 points, 38% - 4, 7.9% - 5 points. points and Answering the question "Estimate your fulfillment of recommendations for a healthy lifestyle and disease prevention" in points, 3.8% of doctors rated themselves with 5 points, 38.5% — with 4 points, 49.0% — with 3 points, 5.8% — with 2 points, 2.9% — with 1 point. To the question "Do you follow the recommendations for a healthy lifestyle?" the following distribution of answers was obtained: 70% of respondents (40% of women and 30% of men) follow the doctor's advice on a healthy lifestyle and preventive recommendations, taking into account individual risk factors (cigarette smoking, alcohol consumption, sedentary lifestyle, occupational risks. 30% of medical professionals who did not follow the advice on a healthy lifestyle indicated the main reasons for this behavior: insufficient motivation (16%), difficulty or unwillingness to get rid of bad habits (smoking, drinking, etc.) (14%). In addition, 98% of health care providers noted that they always provide their patients with recommendations for a healthy lifestyle and risk factor motivation.

According to the results of the study, overweight and obesity were found in 30% of respondents (20% of women and 10% of men). Thus, the prevalence of obesity among medical workers is higher among women than among men ($p < 0.05$).

In the course of the interviews, the impact of stress and psycho-emotional stress during the performance of official duties was clarified. 75% of respondents noted that they often experience stress and psycho-emotional overload at work, do not observe the work and rest regime.

Conclusion.

The following factors play an important role in the formation of a healthy lifestyle for medical workers: individual attitude of a person to the modification of risk factors; giving up bad habits; proper nutrition; observance of work and rest regime, adaptation to stress and stressful situations; implementation of healthy lifestyle recommendations.

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